

CASSETTE Instructions

We've created a Spotify playlist with songs shared by all participants. Your task is to listen to each song and associate it with an emotion. Please write down the song number next to the emotion in the white areas of the wheel of emotions. Then, we'll reveal the initial emotion associated with each song. *Get ready to explore the emotional connections within the music!*

N.R. [wheel of Emotions] IN OUT

Normal Bias 1 1/2

60

On Affect and Mixtapes
Free Associations

AGFA CRX 60

You can make notes here

Tracks | B-side

1. Let There Be Love Today
2. Wall of Eyes
3. Standing Outside a Broken Phone ...
4. Bout to Lose it
5. UrRoom
6. Duvet
7. Waiting for Love